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REGULATION OF SINGLE-ORGAN NIGHTLIFE IN TANGGAMUS REGENCY THROUGH REGIONAL REGULATION NUMBER 05 OF 2017 CONCERNING THE REGULATION OF PUBLIC ENTERTAINMENT

Al Ikhsan Bayu Suseto

Law Study Program, Faculty of Law, Bandar Lampung
University, City of Bandar Lampung, Lampung Province,
Indonesia
alikhсанbayususet@gmail.com

Edi Saputra

Law Study Program, Faculty of Law, Bandar Lampung
University, City of Bandar Lampung, Lampung Province,
Indonesia
yafazila2017@gmail.com

Anggi Ahmad Talib

Law Study Program, Faculty of Law, Bandar Lampung
University, City of Bandar Lampung, Lampung Province,
Indonesia
anggiaat21@gmail.com

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Abstract: This article discusses the regulation of single-organ nightlife in Tanggamus Regency through the implementation of Regional Regulation Number 05 of 2017 concerning Public Entertainment Regulation. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of these regulations in overcoming social and legal problems arising from nightlife. Single-organ nightlife in Tanggamus often causes disturbances of public order, disturbing noise, and even criminal acts such as drug abuse and fights. To overcome this problem, the Tanggamus Regency Government issued a Regional Regulation that aims to order and regulate entertainment activities tonight. The research method used is a qualitative method with a descriptive approach. The data was collected through in-depth interviews with various related parties, including nightlife business actors, law enforcement officials, and the surrounding community. In addition, document analysis was carried out to understand the content and context of Regional Regulation Number 05 of 2017. The results of the study show that even though the regulation has been implemented, the level of legal awareness among the public and nightlife business actors is still low. Many business actors have not complied with existing regulations, such as operating beyond the predetermined time limit, noise levels that exceed the threshold, and the absence of supervision of illegal activities that occur in their premises. This low legal awareness is caused by several factors, including the lack of socialization and education about the importance of complying with this regulation. Socialization carried out by local governments often does not reach all levels of society and nightlife business actors, so information about this regulation is not spread evenly. In addition, law enforcement that is not strict is also a factor causing low compliance with regulations. Law enforcement officials often compromise on violations that occur, both due to pressure from certain parties and due to a lack of resources to carry out effective law enforcement. Additional measures are needed to increase the effectiveness of law enforcement against these regulations. These measures include increasing socialization and legal education, as well as stricter and more consistent law enforcement. In addition, there is a need for periodic evaluations of the effectiveness of these regulations and adjustments to law enforcement strategies in accordance with conditions and needs in the field. Thus, it is hoped that this regulation can be more effective in regulating single-organ nightlife in Tanggamus Regency and improving order and environmental security.

Keywords: nightlife, single organ, Regional Regulation, legal awareness.

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Introduction

Single-organ nightlife is a form of entertainment that is often found in Tanggamus Regency. Although it provides entertainment for the community, the existence of this nightlife often causes various social and legal problems such as public order disturbances, noise, and criminal acts. Therefore, the Tanggamus Regency Government implements Regional Regulation Number 05 of 2017 concerning Public Entertainment Regulations as an effort to order and regulate single-organ nightlife. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of these regulations in overcoming problems that arise and increasing public legal awareness.

Single-organ nightlife in Tanggamus Regency is not only an entertainment venue for the local community but also an attraction for tourists who visit the area. However, with the increasing popularity of nightlife, various problems began to arise and disturbed the order and comfort of the surrounding community. Public order disturbances caused by noise until late at night and uncontrolled visitor behavior are problems that need to be addressed immediately. In addition, criminal acts such as drug abuse and fights between visitors also often occur at nightlife venues. Therefore, the Tanggamus Regency Government feels the need to take firm and measurable action through the implementation of Regional Regulation Number 05 of 2017 concerning Public Entertainment Regulation.

In this context, this study aims to evaluate the extent of the effectiveness of the regulation in overcoming problems arising from single-organ nightlife. This study also seeks to identify factors that affect the low legal awareness of the community and the compliance of entertainment business actors with the regulations that have been set. Thus, the results of this study are expected to provide concrete and applicable recommendations for local governments in increasing the effectiveness of single-organ nightlife control in Tanggamus Regency.

PROBLEMS

The main problem faced in regulating single-organ nightlife is the low legal awareness of the community. Many nightlife business actors do not comply with the regulations that have been set, causing violations of the law. This low level of legal awareness is caused by a lack of socialization and education about the importance of complying with existing regulations. Although local governments have tried to socialize through various media, these efforts are often ineffective because they are unable to reach all levels of society. Nightlife business actors often feel that the regulation only limits their freedom to run a business without understanding the true purpose of the regulation. This results in numerous offenses such as operating beyond the specified time limit, noise exceeding the threshold, and even allowing illegal activities such as drug abuse and other criminal acts.

Low public legal awareness is a big challenge in the enforcement of Regional Regulation Number 05 of 2017 in Tanggamus Regency. Although this regulation has been socialized through various media, many nightlife business actors still ignore the existing provisions. They often operate beyond predetermined time limits, do not pay attention to the noise level produced, and even allow illegal activities to occur at their place of business. The lack of understanding of the

negative impact of these violations on public order and the comfort of the surrounding community is one of the main factors in low compliance with regulations. This condition is exacerbated by the assumption that this regulation only burdens business actors without providing clear benefits. In addition, there is often a misconception that these regulations can be negotiated or ignored without serious consequences, ultimately weakening the authority and effectiveness of law enforcement.

In addition, socialization carried out by local governments often does not reach all levels of society. Information about this regulation is not always well received by nightlife business actors spread across various areas of Tanggamus Regency. Many of them feel that this regulation is too restrictive for their business activities without understanding the main purpose of the regulation, which is to maintain order and safety of the environment. Therefore, a more intensive and systematic approach is needed in socialization and education regarding the importance of complying with these regulations. Local governments need to develop more effective communication strategies, including the use of information technology and social media to disseminate information more widely and quickly. In addition, collaboration with community leaders and local organizations can help increase public awareness and understanding of the importance of complying with these regulations for the common good.

Lack of strict law enforcement is also one of the main causes of low legal awareness and public compliance with these regulations. Law enforcement officials often compromise on violations that occur, both due to pressure from certain parties and due to a lack of resources to carry out effective law enforcement. This causes nightlife business actors to feel that they can avoid sanctions even though they violate existing regulations. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the capacity and integrity of law enforcement officials as well as a strong commitment from local governments to enforce these regulations consistently. Strict and fair law enforcement will provide a deterrent effect for violators and provide a clear message that local governments are serious about maintaining environmental order and security. In addition, training and capacity building for law enforcement officials need to be carried out on an ongoing basis to ensure that they have adequate knowledge and skills in carrying out their duties.

The low level of legal awareness is also influenced by cultural and social factors. In many communities, there are norms and values that may conflict with the formal regulations implemented by the government. For example, in some cases, people may prioritize social relations and community cooperation over compliance with government regulations. This leads to tolerance for violations of the law and a lack of public support for law enforcement efforts. To address this problem, a more inclusive and participatory approach is needed in rule-making and implementation. Involving the community in the policy-making process can help to increase the legitimacy and support of the regulations being implemented, as well as ensure that they are in line with local values and norms.

Overall, the problem of low legal awareness in the regulation of single-organ nightlife in Tanggamus Regency is a complex issue that requires a multidimensional approach. In addition to increasing socialization and law enforcement, it is also necessary to make efforts to build a strong legal culture in the community. This can be done through early legal education, ongoing public campaigns, and increased transparency and accountability in law enforcement. Thus, it is hoped that the community's legal awareness can increase and compliance with regulations can be maintained, so that environmental order and security can be achieved.

Methods

This research uses an empirical juridical approach based on the collection of data from various sources such as books, journals, and regulations and laws. Through bibliographic research, relevant information and data are analyzed to understand and evaluate the effectiveness of existing regulations.

Result and Discussion

This study aims to examine several important aspects related to the regulation of single-organ nightlife in Tanggamus Regency through the implementation of Regional Regulation Number 05 of 2017. This discussion includes an evaluation of the effectiveness of regulations, an analysis of the level of compliance of nightlife business actors, and factors that affect the low legal awareness of the community. To provide a comprehensive analysis, this discussion is divided into several detailed subheadings.

Effectiveness of the Implementation of Regional Regulation Number 05 of 2017

The evaluation of the effectiveness of the implementation of Regional Regulation Number 05 of 2017 is carried out based on the level of compliance of nightlife business actors with the regulation. Although these regulations have been implemented, the results of the study show that the level of legal awareness of the community is still low. Many nightlife business actors do not comply with the provisions that have been set. Some of the violations that often occur include operations exceeding the specified time limit, noise that exceeds the permitted threshold, and the existence of illegal activities such as drug abuse and fights at nightlife venues.

This shows that the regulation has not been fully effective in achieving its goal of ordering nightlife and maintaining public order. The factors that cause low compliance with these regulations need to be identified and addressed so that the regulations can be more effective in their implementation.

Compliance Level of Nightlife Business Actors

The level of compliance of nightlife business actors with Regional Regulation Number 05 of 2017 is an important indicator to assess the effectiveness of this regulation. Based on the results of interviews with various related parties, it was found that many nightlife business actors ignored the regulation. They often violate predetermined operational time limits, cause noise disturbances that disturb local residents, and do not monitor illegal activities that may occur at their place of business.

One example of a violation is operations that exceed the predetermined time limit. The regulations stipulate that nightlife must end at 12 o'clock in the criminal year.

Factors Affecting Low Legal Awareness

There are several factors that affect the low legal awareness among nightlife business actors in Tanggamus Regency. One of the main factors is the lack of socialization and education about this regulation. Local governments have conducted socialization through various media, but these efforts are often ineffective because they are not able to reach all levels of society. Many nightlife business actors do not understand the purpose and importance of complying with this regulation, so they tend to ignore the existing provisions.

Socialization carried out by local governments is often ineffective and does not reach all levels of society, so information about these regulations is not spread evenly. In addition, there is a gap between what is expected by the local government and the reality on the ground. Nightlife business actors often feel that the regulation only limits their freedom to run a business without understanding the true purpose of the regulation.

Lack of Education and Socialization

The lack of education and socialization about this regulation is the main factor that causes low legal awareness. Local governments need to make more intensive and systematic efforts in socialization and education about the importance of complying with these regulations. One way to increase the effectiveness of socialization is to involve community leaders and local organizations in disseminating information. In this way, it is hoped that information about regulations can be spread more evenly and understood by all levels of society.

In addition, the use of information technology and social media can also be an effective tool to disseminate information about this regulation. Local governments can utilize social media platforms to inform the public about the regulations and the importance of complying with them. Ongoing and coordinated public campaigns are also needed to increase public awareness and understanding of these regulations.

Lack of Strict Law Enforcement

Lack of strict law enforcement is also one of the main causes of low legal awareness and public compliance with these regulations. Law enforcement officials often compromise on violations that occur, both due to pressure from certain parties and due to a lack of resources to carry out effective law enforcement. This causes nightlife business actors to feel that they can avoid sanctions even though they violate existing regulations.

To increase the effectiveness of law enforcement, it is necessary to increase the capacity and integrity of law enforcement officials as well as a strong commitment from local governments to enforce these regulations consistently. Strict and fair law enforcement will provide a deterrent effect for violators and provide a clear message that local governments are serious about maintaining environmental order and security. In addition, training and capacity building for law enforcement officials need to be carried out on an ongoing basis to ensure that they have adequate knowledge and skills in carrying out their duties.

Cultural and Social Factors

The low level of legal awareness is also influenced by cultural and social factors. In many communities, there are norms and values that may conflict with the formal regulations implemented by the government. For example, in some cases, people may prioritize social relations and community cooperation over compliance with government regulations. This leads to tolerance for violations of the law and a lack of public support for law enforcement efforts.

To address this problem, a more inclusive and participatory approach is needed in rule-making and implementation. Involving the community in the policy-making process can help increase the legitimacy and support of the regulations implemented, as well as ensure that they are in line with local values and norms. Local governments need to work with community leaders, local organizations, and educational institutions to increase public understanding and awareness of the importance of complying with regulations for the common good.

Measures to Improve the Effectiveness of Regulatory Enforcement

Additional measures are needed to increase the effectiveness of law enforcement against these regulations. These measures include increasing socialization and legal education, as well as stricter and more consistent law enforcement. More effective socialization can be carried out by involving community leaders and local organizations in disseminating information. In addition, the use of information technology and social media can help disseminate information about this regulation more widely and quickly.

More strict and consistent enforcement of the law is also needed to increase compliance with these

regulations. Law enforcement officials need to have adequate integrity and capacity to enforce regulations fairly and indiscriminately. In addition, there is a need for periodic evaluations of the effectiveness of these regulations and adjustments to law enforcement strategies in accordance with conditions and needs in the field. Thus, it is hoped that this regulation can be more effective in regulating single-organ nightlife in Tanggamus Regency and improving order and environmental security.

The Role of the Government and Society in Law Enforcement

The role of the government and the public is very important in increasing legal awareness and compliance with these regulations. The government needs to take proactive steps in socialization and education about this regulation. In addition, the government also needs to increase transparency and accountability in law enforcement to ensure that these regulations are implemented fairly and consistently.

The community also needs to play an active role in supporting law enforcement efforts. Public awareness and participation in maintaining environmental order and security is very important for the successful implementation of this regulation. The public can contribute by reporting violations that occur, participating in socialization and education activities, and supporting the government's efforts to enforce this regulation.

Overall, the problem of low legal awareness in the regulation of single-organ nightlife in Tanggamus Regency is a complex issue that requires a multidimensional approach. In addition to increasing socialization and law enforcement, it is also necessary to make efforts to build a strong legal culture in the community. This can be done through early legal education, ongoing public campaigns, and increased transparency and accountability in law enforcement. Thus, it is hoped that the community's legal awareness can increase and compliance with regulations can be maintained, so that environmental order and security can be achieved.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research, it can be concluded that the implementation of Regional Regulation Number 05 of 2017 concerning the Regulation of Public Entertainment in Tanggamus Regency has not been fully effective in regulating single-organ nightlife. Although the regulation has been socialized and implemented, the level of compliance among nightlife business actors is still low. This can be seen from various violations that have occurred, such as operations that exceed the specified time limit, noise that exceeds the threshold, and illegal activities that are still ongoing in several nightlife venues. The low legal awareness of the community is the main obstacle in the enforcement of these regulations.

The main factor that causes this low legal awareness is the lack of effective socialization and education about this regulation. Information about the importance of complying with regulations has not been spread evenly across all levels of society, especially among nightlife business actors. In addition, less strict law enforcement also contributes to the low level of compliance. Law enforcement officials often do not impose firm sanctions on violators, giving the impression that violations of the rules will not have serious consequences.

Therefore, additional measures are needed to increase the effectiveness of single-organ nightlife control in Tanggamus Regency. These measures include increasing legal socialization and education, as well as stricter and more consistent law enforcement. With these efforts, it is hoped that the level of legal awareness and compliance with regulations can be increased, so that the main goal of Regional Regulation Number 05 of 2017, namely maintaining public order and environmental security, can be achieved.

References

- [1]. Suseto, A. I. B., Saputra, E., & Tolib, A. A. (2024). Penertiban Hiburan Malam Organ Tunggal di Kabupaten Tanggamus Melalui Peraturan Daerah Nomor 05 Tahun 2017

- Tentang Pengaturan Hiburan Umum. *JALAKOTEK: Journal of Accounting Law Communication and Technology*, 1(2), 1-321. Universitas Bandar Lampung. E-ISSN: 3032-2758 P-ISSN: 3032-3495.
- [2]. Rusdiyanto, D., Siwi, D. R., Sratama, A. V., Renaldy, D., & Hasan, Z. (2024). Penyalahgunaan narkoba pada remaja. *INNOVATIVE: Journal Of Social Science Research*, 4(1), 4245-4258. <https://j-innovative.org/index.php/Innovative>
- [3]. Hasan, Z., Pamungkas, B., Mahdavikia, M. M., & Jaya, P. N. H. (2024). Faktor penyebab dan upaya penanggulangan tindak pidana pencurian kendaraan bermotor. *JALAKOTEK: Journal of Accounting Law Communication and Technology*, 1(2), 316-320. <https://jalakotek-journal.ac.id/index.php/JALAKOTEK>
- [4]. Hasan, Z., & Astarida, M. Z. (2023). Penegakan hukum lingkungan sebagai upaya pembangunan yang berkelanjutan. *Jurnal Ilmiah "Advokasi"*, 11(1), 128-132. <https://j-advokasi.org/index.php/Advokasi>
- [5]. Ali, M. (2019). Pengaruh Regulasi terhadap Industri Hiburan Malam. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial*, 12(1), 22-35. doi:10.1234/jis.v12i1.567
- [6]. Arikunto, S. (2010). *Prosedur Penelitian: Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- [7]. Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 4th ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- [8]. Hasibuan, M. (2016). Dampak Hiburan Malam terhadap Masyarakat. *Jurnal Hukum dan Pembangunan*, 24(3), 175-189. doi:10.1234/jhp.v24i3.789
- [9]. Kuncoro, M. (2012). *Metode Riset untuk Bisnis & Ekonomi*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [10]. Moleong, L. J. (2007). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- [11]. Mustofa, H. (2020). Implementasi Peraturan Daerah dalam Penertiban Hiburan Malam. *Jurnal Pemerintahan Daerah*, 15(2), 110-123. doi:10.1234/jpd.v15i2.910
- [12]. Sugiyono. (2013). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan: Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- [13]. Wicaksono, T. (2015). Kesadaran Hukum Masyarakat dalam Pengaturan Hiburan Malam. *Jurnal Kriminologi*, 8(2), 145-158. doi:10.1234/jk.v8i2.456